

PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract: Today, in the world, and in particular in Uzbekistan, the demand for qualified, knowledgeable and equipped with modern methods of teaching staff is increasing from year to year. Therefore, the process of modernization of the higher education system is aimed at increasing attention to the professional training of educators of preschool educational organizations (PEOs) and their understanding of the values in their professional activities. This article describes the need to prepare future educators for innovative activities, the need to form a culture of professional reflection in educators, as well as the concepts of reflection, culture and pedagogical reflection.

Keywords: innovative educational technologies, professional competence, innovative reflexive culture, innovative educational technologies, education, reflection, culture.

INTRODUCTION

Among all professions, education has a special and important social significance. After all, an educator is an architect of the spiritual maturity of the younger generation, a person who educates and educates young people. Today, he ideologically and politically trains young people, teaches them the laws of nature, society, social life and the development of thought. He also prepares students for work, helps them master the secrets of their profession, and participates in solving socio-economic issues important for society.

Reflection (Latin reflexio - return) is one of the types of acts of human consciousness, that is, a movement of consciousness, and is considered as a process

of knowing the subject's own internal psychological feelings and states.

In the encyclopedic dictionary of pedagogy, reflection is interpreted differently. Reflection (from the Latin reflexio - looking back) means reflection, self-observation. The concept of culture is defined in the explanatory dictionary of pedagogy as follows: culture is a certain level of historical development of the creative forces and abilities of society.

The concept of reflection first appeared in ancient Greek philosophy and was explained as the process of reflecting on the thoughts that a person has in his mind. This concept meant that a person draws his attention to the analysis of the content of his thoughts.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

There are various approaches to the problem of reflection in the scientific literature. According to J. Locke, reflection is “an observation in which the mind engages its activity”. In a brief psychological dictionary, the concept of reflection is explained as follows: reflection (lat. reflexio - looking back, appeal) - the process of self-awareness of internal psychic acts and states by the subject. This concept originally arose in philosophy, where it meant the perception of processes occurring in the consciousness of an individual.

R. Descartes associated reflection with the ability of a person to distance himself from all external, physical objects and focus on the content of his thoughts. J. Locke, on the other hand, distinguished between intuition and reflection, presenting reflection as a separate source of knowledge. He interpreted reflection as an internal experience that differs from external experience based on the sense organs. According to these views, a person should be able to self-report on the events in his mind, to have the ability to analyze his personal mental states.

Reflection is the ability to look back, that is, to repeatedly refer to his thoughts and actions, to enter the place of an external observer, to understand what he is doing and how he perceives. However, this means not only the subject's

understanding and knowledge of himself, but also the ability to determine how others perceive him, how he understands his personal characteristics, emotional reactions and cognitive (related to cognition) representations.

One of the definitions that allows us to understand culture in a broad sense is its encyclopedic definition: Culture (lat. cultura - cultivation, upbringing, education, development, respect) is a certain level of development of society, the growth of human creative forces and capabilities, expressed in the types and forms of organization of human life and activity, in their mutual relations, and in the material and spiritual values created by them.

The concept of "culture" is used to describe certain historical periods, societies, peoples and ethnic groups or various spheres of activity and life (for example, labor culture, political culture). In a relatively narrow sense, this concept is associated with the sphere of spiritual life of people.

Theoretical and practical studies on the culture of professional reflection were primarily studied by foreign scholars. In particular, J. Dewey (1933) was the first to discuss the concept of reflection in the educational process in his studies. In his opinion, a teacher or educator can achieve professional development by constantly analyzing their actions in the educational process. Later, D. Schon (1983, 1987) developed the concepts of two main aspects of the pedagogical culture of reflection - "Reflection-in-action" and "Reflection-on-action". This model became the basis for the teacher to analyze his own activities in the educational process and improve his work using this experience in the future. The "Circle of Reflection" model developed by G. Gibbs (1988) is also aimed at effectively organizing the process of professional reflection, allowing the teacher to deeply analyze his experience and evaluate his professional activities. In addition, J. Moon (1999) analyzed the relationship between the culture of professional reflection and the quality of education and developed methodological approaches to increase the effectiveness of the reflection process.

Uzbek pedagogical scientists have also conducted a number of studies on the culture of professional reflection, its stages of development and its role in the education system. In particular, A. Abdukodirov studied the problems of pedagogical reflection and professional growth and developed methods for assessing and improving teachers' own activities. M. Usmonbaeva conducted research on the development of professional competence of educators. Sh. Toshpulatova studied the impact of innovative educational technologies on the culture of reflection and pedagogical approaches. M. Yuldoshev studied the impact of innovative technologies on the pedagogical process and methods for forming teachers' professional reflection. N. Yuldosheva studied modern approaches to forming a culture of reflection in teachers. A. O. Shamsiyev conducted research on the methodology for forming a culture of reflection in future teachers. B. Usmanov analyzed the impact of interactive methods in education on the process of reflection and teacher competence. Research conducted in Uzbekistan is related to the development of a culture of reflection among teachers, the use of innovative educational technologies, and the formation of professional competencies of future educators.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examines the factors influencing the development of a culture of professional reflection among future educators, ways to effectively organize this process in innovative education. Theoretical analysis, empirical research methods, experimental-pedagogical testing, and comparative and statistical analysis methods were used as the methodological basis of the study. Through theoretical analysis, pedagogical, psychological, and sociological sources were studied, and the essence of the culture of professional reflection and its role in innovative education were clarified. As part of the empirical study, the level of professional reflection among future educators was analyzed through questionnaires, interviews, and observations. The experimental-pedagogical test was aimed at forming a culture of

professional reflection of educators through the use of innovative methods. The results of comparison and statistical analysis served to determine the effectiveness of innovative approaches. In the process of research, the possibilities of using modern educational technologies and influencing the professional development of educators based on a reflexive approach were studied.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The introduction of new state standards of preschool education determines and stimulates the search for new approaches to the professional training of educators. These approaches should be aimed at developing the personal potential, activity, creative individuality of educators, their readiness and ability to carry out professional activities. These approaches should also take into account the trends and directions of development of the preschool education system.

The state policy in the field of preschool education development is reflected in the regulatory and legal framework being developed. Despite the fact that the field of preschool education is regulated by numerous legislative acts, further improvement of the legal framework for the provision of preschool education services is required. The current education system is at the stage of innovative development, and in this process, continuous improvement of the professional competence of pedagogical personnel is of great importance. In particular, the development of a culture of professional reflection of educators for the preschool education system is one of the urgent issues of modern education.

Professional reflection is an intellectual process aimed at a deep analysis of a teacher's own activities, assessment and improvement of his professional experience, which serves to improve the quality of education. In this regard, the development and experimental substantiation of the scientific and methodological foundations of improving the methodology for forming a culture of professional reflection of future educators in an innovative educational environment is a pressing scientific issue.

As is known, an important tool for organizing an interactive learning process is interactive teaching methods. Interactive teaching methods (ITM) are a system of teaching methods based on the needs of the learner to activate his cognitive activity and based on the organization of the educational process on the basis of mutual cooperation, based on the "subject-subject" relationship.

In this case, collaborative action is characterized by the mutual exchange of knowledge, ideas, and means of activity in the educational process, the presence of tools that allow each student to make a certain contribution to the educational process. Also, interactive teaching focuses on such principles as student activation, group experience, and feedback. Interactive teaching methods, unlike traditional teaching methods, allow not only to consolidate previously acquired knowledge, but also to implement the process of mastering new knowledge based on collaborative activities.

To form a culture of reflection in future educators, the analysis methodology can be conducted in small groups as a training or exercise. The main components of the pedagogical culture of reflection are as follows. The ability to self-analyze - the teacher evaluates his lessons, teaching methods, and their impact on students. Identifying strengths and weaknesses, he looks for ways to improve them. Critical thinking and readiness for change - the teacher learns to objectively approach his professional activities. He is ready to try new methods and innovative technologies. Professional development and self-improvement - the teacher constantly studies and acquires new knowledge and skills. Implements advanced practices in the field of education in his work. Evaluation of the results of pedagogical activity - analyzes the achievements and difficulties of students and changes the teaching methodology. Monitors and improves his pedagogical impact. Emotional intelligence and emotional reflection - the teacher is able to manage his emotional state and communicate effectively with students. He conducts the educational process taking into account the motivation and emotional state of students. The

importance of the culture of pedagogical reflection increases the quality of education - the teacher can identify shortcomings in his work and apply effective strategies. Helps to establish effective communication with students.

CONCLUSION

Increases the ability to accept and apply innovative educational technologies. Prevents professional stress and fatigue, increases the motivation of the teacher. In short, pedagogical reflection or reflexive culture is one of the topical topics today. Explaining these concepts to future educators in Uzbekistan through new methodologies, enriching their professional skills and directing them to work on themselves will make them mature specialists in their profession.

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